

Supplementary Information

Pitfalls in sample preparation of metalloproteins for low-temperature EPR – the example of alkaline myoglobin

Ilenia Serra^{1,2}, Inés García Rubio^{2,3}, Sabine Van Doorslaer¹

¹ BIMEF Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Antwerp, 2610 Antwerp, Belgium

² Department of Condensed Matter Physics, Faculty of Sciences, University of Zaragoza, 50009 Zaragoza, Spain

³ Centro Universitario de la Defensa, 50090 Zaragoza, Spain

Ilenia Serra

Ilenia.Serra@uantwerpen.be

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4537-9635>

Corresponding authors:

Sabine Van Doorslaer

sabine.vandoorslaer@uantwerpen.be

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1685-9202>

Inés García Rubio

inesgr@unizar.es

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1827-1250>

Fig. S1 CW X-band EPR spectrum (low-spin region only) of myoglobin in glycine buffer 50 mM, without and with 20 % (v/v) of glycerol

Fig. S2 CW X-band EPR spectrum of myoglobin in carbonate-bicarbonate buffer 50 mM, in presence of 20 % (v/v) of glycerol. For clarity, the inset of the high-field region is 5x-magnified

Fig. S3 Details of the g_z feature of the OH-ligated LS of myoglobin samples prepared in glycine, CAPS and CHES buffer, respectively, in presence of different glassing agents. Spectra were normalized at the center of the line. Cyan: no cryoprotectant added; red: 20 % glycerol; dark yellow: 20% ethylene glycol; purple: 0.36 M sucrose; green: 0.36 M trehalose

Fig. S4 CW X-band EPR spectrum of myoglobin in carbonate-bicarbonate buffer 50 mM, in the presence of different cryoprotectants. Cyan: no cryoprotectant added; red: 20 % glycerol; dark yellow: 20% ethylene glycol; purple: 0.36 M sucrose; green: 0.36 M trehalose. For clarity, the inset of the high-field region is 5x-magnified

Fig. S5 Exemplary curve-fitting of 2-pulse echo decay spectra at the g_z position of myoglobin samples prepared in CAPS buffer with different cryoprotectants. Blue: experimental spectrum; red: fitted curve

Cryoprotectant	T_m (ns)
None	205 ± 9
20 % glycerol	338 ± 8
20 % ethylene glycol	356 ± 15
0.36 M sucrose	251 ± 6
0.36 M trehalose	286 ± 5

Table S1 T_m values calculated from coefficient B of equation [1] (see main text, experimental section). Errors were estimated using a semi-empirical approach, taking into account the 95 % confidence interval of the fitting and T_m values obtained by performing the fitting on spectra with different starting points chosen arbitrarily within the first ~ 80 ns

MW Pulses length, $t_{\pi/2} - t_{\pi}$ (ns)	T_m (ns)
16-32	332 ± 15
50-100	350 ± 17
80-160	331 ± 10
96-192	338 ± 8

Fig. S6 X-band 2-pulse spin echo decay (left panel) and T_m values obtained from curve-fitting (right panel) of myoglobin samples prepared in CAPS buffer with 20 % (v/v) glycerol, measured at the g_z position with MW pulses of different length. Spectra were normalized at $\tau = 244$ ns. Errors were estimated using a semi-empirical approach, taking into account the 95 % confidence interval of the fitting and T_m values obtained by performing the fitting on spectra with different starting points chosen arbitrarily within the first ~ 80 ns

Fig. S7 Optical spectra of myoglobin in different alkaline buffers at room temperature. Red: 20 % glycerol; dark yellow: 20% ethylene glycol; purple: 0.36 M sucrose; green: 0.36 M trehalose. For clarity, spectra were normalised at $\lambda = 280$ nm and insets were 5x-magnified